

Grain yield response to N (kg grain/kg N) in semidwarf scented rice varieties. DRR, Hyderabad, India. 1990-92 WS.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)				N response (kg grain/kg N)				Nutrient response (kg grain/kg NPK)			
	1990	1991	1992	Mean	1990	1991	1992	Mean	1990	1991	1992	Mean
<i>Variety</i>												
Haryana Basmati 1	3.3	3.1	3.2	3.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pusa Basmati 1	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Kasturi 3.0	3.0	3.0	3.5	3.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Basmati 370	2.4	1.9	2.4	2.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CD (0.05)	0.2	0.1	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>N level (kg N/ha)</i>												
0	1.9	1.9	2.3	2.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
30	2.8	2.7	2.7	2.7	29.7	24.7	14.0	22.8	7.4	6.3	3.6	5.7
60	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.1	21.0	18.3	16.0	18.4	8.4	7.3	6.4	7.4
90	3.5	3.1	4.0	3.5	17.7	13.8	18.9	16.8	8.8	6.9	9.4	8.4
120	3.3	3.0	3.3	3.2	11.8	9.4	8.8	10.0	6.6	5.3	5.0	5.6
CD (0.05)	0.2	0.1	0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Incremental doses of N increased grain yield significantly up to 90 kg N/ha, after which it declined. The response to N during the second and third years was low because of stem borer damage, especially in high N treatments. Despite

these variations, the mean grain yield responses to N averaged over different varieties at 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha were 22.8, 18.4, 16.8, and 10.0 kg grain/kg N, respectively. The mean grain yield response to NPK at 30, 60, 90, and 120

kg N/ha irrespective of variety used averaged 5.7, 7.4, 8.4, and 5.6 kg grain/kg NPK, respectively.

The three semidwarf scented rice varieties recorded positive grain yield response to N up to 90 kg N/ha. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Effect of methods of *Sesbania aculeata* incorporation and nitrogen levels on lowland rice yield

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We studied the effect of different methods of in situ incorporation of green manure *S. aculeata* and three N levels on rice yields in two successive field trials, Sep 1992-Jan 1993 and Jun-Sep 1993. Rice cultivars used were ADT38 (135 d) and IR50 (105 d).

Soil of the experimental field in the first season was clay loam with pH 7.9,

EC 0.5 dS/m, 0.69% organic C, and 205 kg available N/ha, 8 kg available P/ha, and 411 kg available K/ha. Soil in the second season was clay loam with pH 7.8, EC 0.5 dS/m, 0.63% organic C, and 238 kg available N/ha, 7.3 kg available P/ha, and 375 kg available K/ha.

Different methods of in situ green manure incorporation at 45 d of growth were tested. Nitrogen contributed through green manure was 47.3 kg/ha in the first

Effects of methods of *S. aculeata* incorporation in situ and N levels on rice yield.^a 1992-93.

Treatment	Panicles/m ² (no.)		Filled grains/panicle (no.)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2
<i>Main plot</i>								
<i>Incorporation method</i>								
Sickle cutting + country plow	274	510	89.2	68.2	4.5	4.6	5.8	5.9
Animal-drawn Burmese setoon	246	516	85.3	68.6	4.2	4.6	5.4	6.0
Power tiller-operated cagewheel	264	555	88.4	70.4	5.44	5.1	5.7	6.6
Tractor-drawn cagewheel	305	561	90.4	70.8	5.2	5.3	6.7	7.0
LSD (0.05)	5	8	0.5	0.5	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2
<i>Subplot</i>								
<i>(N level (kg/ha))</i>								
0	249	509	84.6	64.9	3.5	3.9	4.6	5.1
50	275	541	88.3	70.2	4.8	5.0	6.1	6.4
100	293	557	92.0	73.5	5.5	5.9	7.0	7.6
LSD (0.05)	2	2	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2

^aInteractions were not significant.

season and 61.2 kg/ha in the second season. In both seasons, 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha were applied to rice as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash. The experiments were laid out in a split-plot design with four replications (see table).

Method of incorporation significantly influenced yield attributes and grain and

straw yields. Tractor-drawn cagewheel incorporation positively influenced rice productivity compared with the other methods (see table). This influence may be because of deeper incorporation (12.5 cm in the first season and 16.7 cm in the second season), which reduced considerably the loss of N and increased N availability to rice, resulting in higher yields.

Grain yield increased by 0.76 t/ha with tractor-drawn cagewheel incorporation and 0.30 t/ha with power tiller incorporation over animal-drawn implement incorporation. Tractor-drawn cagewheel incorporation with 100 kg added N/ha contributed to the highest yield in both seasons. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Mass culture of *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill. on rice hull

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Beauveria bassiana (Bals.) Vuill. shows potential as a biocontrol agent for many

Growth pattern (mean + SD conidial density $\times 10^7$ /ml) of *Beauveria bassiana* on rice hull on different days of inoculation.

Amount of substrate	Days after inoculation			
	15	30	35	40
1/2 bag (180 g) (A)	1.50 $\pm$ 0.14	5.80 $\pm$ 0.60	5.00 $\pm$ 0.12	3.90 $\pm$ 0.27
3/4 bag (270 g) (B)	1.20 $\pm$ 0.19	5.00 $\pm$ 0.20	5.00 $\pm$ 0.11	4.90 $\pm$ 0.24

CV (%) = 7.71; $CD_{0.01}$ (between A and B) = 0.1907 and (between days) = 0.2696.

insect pests of rice. To harvest large quantities of propagule to apply in the field, an easy, inexpensive process for mass culturing was developed. An autoclavable polypropylene bag (33 $\times$

17.5 cm) and a 3.5-cm-long $\times$ 3.2-cm-diameter piece of hollow dry bamboo are required.

The bamboo piece was fitted on the mouth of the bag with twine or a rubber band (see figure). Nonabsorbent cotton was used for plugging. Half to 3/4 of the bag was filled with rice hull (soaked in water overnight), 2% dextrose, and 0.05% chloramphenicol. Bags were sterilized at 20 lb pressure for 20 min, repeated for two consecutive days.

Inoculation was made with 1 ml of a 1.17×10^7 conidia/ml suspension and incubated at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 40 d. The bags were shaken thoroughly every 5 d for uniform growth of fungus. Conidial population was determined at 15, 30, 35, and 40 d after inoculation (DAI).

Twenty grams of substrate, obtained after thoroughly mixing the contents within each bag, was mixed in 70 ml of double-distilled water using Rottery mixture (Remi Motors, Remi Udyog, Bombay) for 20 min. The homogenate was filtered through muslin cloth and then through filter paper (Whatman no. 1). Conidia were counted from the filtrate using a haemocytometer (Naubauer, Fein-oplique, Beankenberg, GDR). The experiment was replicated five times and data were analyzed in a factorial complete randomized design.

Maximum fungal growth was obtained after 30-35 DAI (see table). Half-filled polypropylene bags yielded

Mass culturing *B. bassiana* on rice hull in an autoclavable polypropylene bag, a) hollow bamboo top, b) cotton plug, and c) polypropylene bag with hollow bamboo top and cotton plug fitted on the mouth.